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“Diversity in Biochemistry”

Immunohistochemical assesment of folate and B₁₂ inhibiting non-oncologic drugs influence on cancer

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Purpose was to investigate the effect of metformin, caffeine, itraconazole and nitroglycerin, which are established non-oncologic drugs¹⁻², on an *in vivo* solid tumor model of fibrosarcoma in hamsters. Thirty Syrian golden hamsters of both sexes with the approximate body weight of 100g were randomly distributed in 4 experimental and 1 control groups, with 6 animals in each group. BHK-21/C13 cells were injected subcutaneously into the back of each animal in 5 groups. The experimental groups were treated with metformin, caffeine, itraconazole and nitroglycerin via a gastric tube on a daily basis, immediately after tumor inoculation. Ki-67-positivity and cytoplasmic marker (CD34, COX4, GLUT1, iNOS) immunoeexpression in the tumor samples were quantified. Metformin, caffeine, itraconazole and nitroglycerin diminished tumor mitosis ($p < 0.05$), vasculature ($p < 0.05$) tissue penetration, and increased necroses in tumor slices. Folate and B₁₂ inhibiting nontoxic drugs, might be effective non-toxic agents in anticancer adjuvant and relapse prevention therapy.

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